

When heated slightly with concentrated sulphuric acid, the above compound evolves copious vapour of iodine. Its alcoholic solution gives a deep green colouration with ferric chloride. It gives a green colouration with Million's reagent. When its solution in chloroform is shaken with 10 per cent nitric acid and the mixture allowed to stand for sometime, the chloroform acquires a violet-red colour and the nitric acid becomes somewhat yellow. Similar test with Vioform, under identical conditions, was done and it was found that the chloroform layer acquires the violet-red colour earlier than with the present compound, indicating that possibly the iodine atom in the present compound is more strongly bound than that in Vioform.

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BENGAL IMMUNITY RESEARCH LABORATORY,
CALCUTTA.

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QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART VIII.

BY T. N. GHOSH, S. BANERJEE AND S. L. LASKER

By applying Skraup's reaction some hydroxyquinoline derivatives have been prepared directly from the corresponding nitro compounds.

In connection with some synthetic work, it was found necessary to prepare some chlorohydroxyquinoline derivatives. By following Skraup's method these quinoline derivatives have now been prepared directly from the corresponding nitro compounds. The application of Skraup's reaction in which the amine can be dispensed with and the corresponding nitro compound alone used with success is of interest both from the technical and theoretical point of view, the cost of reduction of the nitro compound being an important factor. Dey and Goswami (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 533) have converted nitrocoumarin into related quinolines without using amino coumarin.

The results obtained are summarised below :

Nitro compound (50 g.)	Quinoline derivative	Yield (uncrystallised)	M.p. (Crystallised)	Analysis	
				Found.	Calc.
(1) <i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	8-Hydroxyquinoline	5 g.	73-74°	N, 9.48	9.65%
(2) <i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	Nil
(3) 4-Chloro-2-nitro-phenol	5-Chloro-8-hydroxy-quinoline	18 g.	122°-123°	N, 7.61	7.82%
(4) 4 : 6-Dichloro-2-nitrophenol	5 : 7-Dichloro-8-hydroxyquinoline	16-18 g.	178°-179°	N, 6.84	6.67%
(5) 2-Chloro-4-nitro-phenol	5-Chloro-6-hydroxy-quinoline	14 g.	197°-198°	N, 7.69	7.83%

According to Simon (*Compt. rend.*, 1907, 144, 138), the mechanism of Skraup's reaction is based on the acrolein produced reacting with amine to give a dihydroquinoline whence by loss of hydrogen quinoline results.

The above scheme of Skraup's reaction is supported by quinaldine synthesis of Doebner and Miller (*Ber.*, 1881, 14, 2816; 1883, 16, 1664; 1884, 17, 1712). However, this scheme does not explain the synthesis of quinoline derivatives directly from the corresponding nitro compounds.

By heating nitrobenzene with concentrated sulphuric acid, Brunner and Vuilleumier (*Schweiz. Woch. Chem. Pharm.*, 1908, 46, 434) have obtained *p*-aminophenol-sulphonic acid. This has been explained as being due to an oxygen atom of the nitrobenzene wandering to the *para*-position and then reduction occurring by the sulphur dioxide produced from the sulphuric acid and phenol.

Concentrated sulphuric acid is known to convert alizarin and other hydroxy-derivatives of anthraquinone into tri- and hexahydroxy derivatives. It acts as an oxidising agent. Similarly sulphuric acid can be assumed to be reduced to sulphurous acid, which reduces the nitro compound to the amino compound to start the reaction. Subsequent reduction of the nitro compound to amino derivative after the reaction has once started is possibly due to the hydrogen arising in the reaction as outlined by Simon. The reaction, however, appears to be facilitated by the presence of chlorine atom in the benzene nucleus.

EXPERIMENTAL

The quinoline derivatives, described in this paper, are known. The reactions as recorded in this paper have all been carried out under identical experimental conditions. The general method of procedure followed is given below in case of one particular preparation.

5-Chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline.—Glycerine (140 g.), made anhydrous by heating at 180° (thermometer in liquid) for 30 minutes, was mixed to a paste by shaking with well-powdered 2-nitro-4-chlorophenol (50 g.), to which pure, concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84; 60 g.) was added dropwise with shaking. The mixture was then heated under reflux on a sand-bath with occasional shaking, when a heavy dark liquid was obtained. As soon as the reaction commenced with frothing and evolution of fumes, the flask was taken away from the sand-bath to avoid too vigorous a reaction. After the reaction had subsided, the flask was heated under reflux on the sand-bath for 2 hours with frequent shaking.

The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and the lumps were broken. Pure, concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84; 60 g.) was then added drop by drop with shaking and the mixture was heated under reflux on the sand-bath for 4 hours, the flask being removed from the sand-bath when the reaction tended to become vigorous.

Next day the dark mass was taken out of the flask and thoroughly triturated with sufficient quantity of warm water in a mortar. The mixture was filtered and the clear aqueous solution was treated with sodium carbonate till distinctly alkaline.

A solid was obtained, which was filtered and washed thoroughly with cold water. This operation was repeated two or three times. Total yield 18 g. The product dissolves readily in dilute hydrochloric acid and is precipitated by sodium carbonate. It was crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in needles, m.p. 122-23°. (Found: N, 7.61. Calc. for C_9H_8ONCl : N, 7.82 per cent).

8-Hydroxyquinoline.—In preparing this compound, the reaction mixture was treated with sodium carbonate till distinctly alkaline. The whole mixture was then distilled in steam when the above quinoline derivative was obtained in the distillate. It was filtered and finally crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 73°-74°.

2-Chloro-4-nitrophenol.—To an acetic acid solution of *p*-nitrophenol (14 g.), cooled in ice, dry chlorine gas was passed till the increase in weight came up to 4 g. The solution was then poured into large quantity of water when a heavy oil was precipitated, which soon solidified on scratching. It was filtered and crystallised from 50% alcohol in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 110-11°. (Found: N, 7.73. $C_6H_4O_3NCl$ requires N, 8.09 per cent).

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